

AGROTECHNIQUES FOR ALIMURGICAL PLANTS

1. *Cichorium intybus* 2. *Urtica dioica* 3. *Clematis vitalba* 4. *Silene vulgaris*

THE WHAT AND WHY

Alimurgy, this unknown - Aside their cultural and environmental heritage, locally linked to past food systems, the alimurgical plant species currently represent an opportunity to develop short value chains in rural contexts with high natural values. An interesting strategy at the farm level is the cultivation of alimurgical plants in agroforestry systems. Alimurgy, from the Latin "alimentia urgentia", refers to the nutritional opportunity offered by a number of wild plant species. About 10% of the world flora is known as edible. This would correspond to roughly 50,000 species. Just in Italy, a biodiversity hotspot amid the Mediterranean basin, more than 800 species are recognised edible. Whatever the exact numbers, many alimurgical species are known and used just at the local level, thus representing a reservoir of opportunities for the development of local economies. Especially, the harvest of wild species provides occasions in the eco-touristic and gastronomic fields.

Keywords: Wild edible plants, Mediterranean orchards, short value chain, agritourism, recreational services, nutraceutical products

HOW THE CHALLENGE IS ADDRESSED

Allied crops in orchards - Various Mediterranean orchards are prone to the alimurgy, owing to the wide spacing and to the recommended practice of greening. The majority of alimurgical species are poliennial, adapted to coexist with other plants. This is why they do not require violent tillage practices. Minimum or no-tillage techniques can be adopted to protect the soil through the greening. The spontaneous dissemination of alimurgical species is often sufficient to preserve over years the productive potential. In addition, spontaneous grasses are adaptable to different light environments. Concerning the water economy, the alliance with trees is beneficial to the herbs due to both the tree shadowing and hydraulic lift. Finally, the rusticity of the alimurgical species does not require particular fertilization or phytochemical defence.

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ADVANTAGES

The cultivation of alimurgical species through the adoption of greening techniques in orchards and groves with relatively low tree density adds a significant income for the farmer. The harvest of high added value wild edible plants becomes abundant and relatively cheap, in terms of labour. However, it should be taken in mind that any farmer's increased revenue is strictly related to the kind of value chain the alimurgical products are enclosed in. Especially, the short value chains have the capacity to magnify the added value of such products. The closest the producer to the final consumer the highest the added value. In local experiences, this rule appears particularly true when the alimurgical farm is in direct contact with food transformation laboratories and catering activities. In the case of agritouristic farms, the food transformation and the catering can be integrated in the farm activities. Further, organising the direct selling of the fresh product is an effective short value chain, with evident advantages for both the farmer and the consumer. However, in order to achieve this proximity in the supply chain, the farm must be effectively set up for direct sales. This means that the farm has the necessary workforce to manage the sales. Furthermore, the business location must be easily identifiable and accessible to potential buyers. An additional advantage related to the production of edible wild species within the farm is represented by the possibility of providing a more exquisitely cultural type of service alongside the more specific food-related one. In fact, agritourism and farms that respond to consumer demand coming from urbanized areas can easily stimulate and satisfy that cultural consumption demand. This need of a cultural kind is already pronounced in communities that have lost their ancestral rural roots. In particular, the organization of theoretical and practical courses, as well as campaigns for the harvesting and culinary preparation of edible wild species, can find enthusiastic responses from urbanized consumers. Thus, alongside food production, the wild food farm demonstrates the ability to provide ecosystem services that are also recreational and cultural in nature.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Nutritional opportunity offered by a number of wild plant species**
- **Mediterranean orchards are prone to alimurgical greening**
- **The short value chains have the capacity to magnify the added value of alimurgy**

Homage to Bernini. As in the famous colonnade of Saint Peter's Square in Vatican City you can see only the front columns, in this almond plantation you see just the front trees. Placed in Maremma, the plantation is ideal for alimurgical productions in agroforestry.

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